

EFL Teachers' Metacognitive Awareness as a Predictor of Their Professional Success

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Abstract : Metacognitive knowledge increases EFL students' ability to be successful learners. Although this relationship has been investigated by a number of scholars, EFL teachers' explicit awareness of their cognitive knowledge has not been sufficiently explored. The aim of this study was to examine the role of EFL teachers' metacognitive knowledge in their pedagogical performance. Furthermore, the role played by years of their academic education and teaching experience was also studied. Fifty female EFL teachers were selected. They completed Metacognitive Awareness Inventory (MAI) that assessed six components of metacognition including procedural knowledge, declarative knowledge, conditional knowledge, planning, evaluating, and management strategies. Near the end of the academic semester, the students of each class filled in 'the Language Teacher Characteristics Questionnaire' to evaluate their teachers' pedagogical performance. Four elements of MAI, declarative knowledge, planning, evaluating, and management strategies were found to be significantly correlated with EFL teachers' pedagogical success. Significant correlation was also established between metacognitive knowledge and EFL teachers' years of academic education and teaching experience. The findings obtained from this research have contributing implication for EFL teacher educators. The discussion concludes by setting out directions for future research.

Keywords : metacognitive knowledge, pedagogical performance, language teacher characteristics questionnaire, metacognitive awareness inventory

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